

Technical Instruction

Simple Quantification of Green Space with GIS

Leibniz Institute of
Ecological Urban and
Regional Development

Introduction

The monitoring and evaluation of environmental management practices such as restoration, conservation and reforestation is a major part of sustainable planning. Unfortunately, the quantification of large areas of green space over time can be both time-consuming and complex. Here simple GIS and remote sensing methods of land cover classification and NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) can be used to obtain a practical overview of temporal and areal changes for further ecological research and decision-making.

Data & software requirements

Data

The following instruction is based on land cover classification and optical remote sensing data, which can be obtained from various open data sources in medium to high resolution. The choice of land cover datasets is determined by the geographical scale, the relevant time periods and desired image resolution for the examined region. In many cases, classification data must be created ad hoc from remote sensing imagery to meet the desired requirements. Since the focus of this instruction is on vegetation and green space, the temporal influences of the seasons and phenological cycles should be given due weight when choosing the investigated time period. The processing of remote sensing imagery to determine land cover is a separate topic for which many online resources are available (see appendix). The NDVI can be calculated and downloaded from the same remote sensing data used to create the land cover classification. Typical data sources for satellite imagery and land cover data are also given in the appendix.

Software

The processing of spatial data can be done by any standard GIS (Geographic Information System) software. Typical examples are the open source *QGIS* or the licensed *ArcGIS Pro* from ESRI. These support a wide range of data formats and provide tools to further process raster and vector data. They also provide workflows to perform land cover classification from remote sensing imagery and raster calculations to derive optical indices such as NDVI.

Quantifying green space and reforestation through land cover classification

The development of green spaces and reforestation practices can be easily quantified by calculating the changing extent of particular classes of land cover over time (Zhu et al., 2022). For this, the number of pixels per class (e.g. forest, grassland or sealed surface) can be taken from the attribute table of the dataset. Then the spatial extent can be simply calculated by multiplying this number with the area (in km²) per pixel, which is predefined by the resolution of the underlying remote sensing data. To identify changes in land cover, datasets from different time stamps can be compared using change detection software tools (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Detection of land cover change of Beiyang Township in Huangyan-Taizhou, China, highlighting the expansion and contraction in forested areas

NDVI – Normalized Difference Vegetation Index

The NDVI is a common index based on optical remote sensing data. Reflecting the presence of chlorophyll, it is a metric for plant productivity and biomass production (Tucker and Sellers, 1986), and thus green space and volume. While most GIS software is able to automatically generate an NDVI, it can also easily be derived using a raster-/band-calculation tool. For such manual calculation of the NDVI, remote sensing data is needed that includes spectral bands in the red and near-infrared spectrum, which is standard for most satellite systems.

Figure 2: NDVI of Beiyang Township in Huangyan-Taizhou, China for Dec 2020, derived from Landsat 8 imagery – colours adjusted to emphasize differences between land cover and vegetation density: < 0 – water, < 0.1 – bare soil/urban area, > 0.1 – vegetation of different types and density

Since the NDVI not only captures green vegetation but all types of land cover, the index's scale will vary depending on the local environment. Therefore, additional information (such as from land cover maps or aerial images) are needed to interpret the NDVI image, especially in heterogeneous areas (Gascon et al., 2016) (Fig. 2). The impact of the spatial resolution of the image should also be considered (Martinez and Labib, 2023). To take account of phenological cycles and other growth factors, the NDVI should be summarized as a mean over several months before analyzing the index over several years.

Despite the many factors to be considered when calculating and interpreting the NDVI, it is still a straight-forward method that offers a qualitative estimate of the density and health of green spaces in any analysis of land cover change. For more detailed explanations of the individual processing steps and interpretation, see the references to NDVI in the appendix.

Literature

- Gascon, M., Cirach, M., Martínez, D., Dadvand, P., Valentín, A., Plasència, A., Nieuwenhuijsen, M.J., 2016. Normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) as a marker of surrounding greenness in epidemiological studies: The case of Barcelona city. *Urban For. Urban Green.* 19, 88–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2016.07.001>
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Data sources for satellite imagery & land cover data

- **USGS-Earth Explorer**
30m Landsat satellite imagery, Land Cover, NDVI
<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/>
 - **Copernicus Browser**
10m Sentinel 2 satellite imagery
<https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/>
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Literature & software tutorials on land cover classification and NDVI calculation

- **Step-by-Step: Land Cover Change Detection through Supervised Classification**
<https://www.un-spider.org/advisory-support/recommended-practices/recommended-practice-land-cover-change/step-by-step>
- **Land Cover Change Detection with Supervised Classification in QGIS**
https://dges.carleton.ca/CUOSGwiki/index.php/Land_Use_Land_Cover_Change_Detection_with_Supervised_classification_in_QGIS
- **Arset – Land Cover Classification with Satellite Imagery**
<https://appliedsciences.nasa.gov/get-involved/training/english/arset-land-cover-classification-satellite-imagery>
- **ESRI ArcGIS Pro: NDVI Documentation**
Calculation & Interpretation with ArcGIS Pro Software
<https://pro.arcgis.com/de/pro-app/latest/help/analysis/raster-functions/ndvi-function.htm>
- **Sentinel Hub**
Examples on NDVI calculation for different satellite systems
<https://custom-scripts.sentinel-hub.com/custom-scripts/sentinel-2/ndvi/>
- **USGS: Landsat NDVI**
Data sheet of NDVI products derived from 30m Landsat-Satellite Imagery
<https://www.usgs.gov/landsat-missions/landsat-normalized-difference-vegetation-index>

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